

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

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**Work processes checklists for
circular construction**

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches reusing precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in four European countries. This report - work processes checklists - is intended as a practical guide for firms in the construction sector to make the transition to reuse of materials and components. The deliverable is based on the experiences of the real-life pilots of the ReCreate project. Emphasised are processes regarding communication, data collection and material handling.

Reuse of materials and components in industrialised construction is a relatively new phenomenon which, regarding work processes, has largely only been studied in the ReCreate project. For the foreseeable future, deconstruction will remain manual labour, although significantly assisted by (digital) tools and machines. In the work processes related to deconstruction, there are small and big details attached to the execution of work. This deliverable will describe these in generalised terms, because a fact of reuse is that each building is a unique project, which needs more or less customised solutions.

However, slightly detached from the physical work processes is the flow of information between actors in a deconstruction project. This has been identified as the signature difference with linear construction and demolition. The flow of information has been conceptualised already (see Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023), and the pilot projects in the ReCreate project have provided empirical backing for this conceptualisation.

The basis of this work practice checklists report is the empirical material gathered for the scientific study of work process as well as reflections on work processes with the industrial partners of the four project countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany). This basis ensures that, for the case of reuse of concrete elements, these checklists have a sound basis in the real world.

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List of abbreviations

A	Architect
C	Construction company
D	Deconstruction company
L	Logistics provider
LA	Local authorities
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment (consultant)
MT	Material testing consultant
R	Refurbishment provider
SE	Structural engineer

1. Introduction

Work processes in the circular construction economy require communication and data sharing between actors and attention to detail. Although only a modest amount of truly new skills is needed, engaging in circular construction projects is not without complexity. This work processes checklists report aims to provide focal actors in circular construction with a collection of central questions they should ponder when engaging with the transition to circularity. Ideally, these checklists should be part of the planning phase of the project. This introduction provides a short guidance on how to use the checklists.

The core difference between linear and circular modes of production is that work processes in various stages of the production process matter much more, and reflexively. This means that an actor in one stage of the project should have a clear understanding of what actors in other stages do and what they need in terms of guidance or information. These information needs may concern earlier or later phases of the project. In the linear economy, the existence of standardised products reduces the need this kind of interaction: sufficient information can be found from 'the market' because product characteristics are easily accessible from producers or sellers. By contrast, in the circular economy, products and processes are almost by default customised. In the ReCreate project, considerable effort has gone into determining the sufficient and necessary quality management tests, which can produce information on harvested concrete elements and how they can be reused.

For these reasons, it is important to plan a circular construction project well. This involves the actors performing the work but also contacts with relevant authorities. Central to the processes is, however, the donor building, which will provide the reusable materials and products. What happens with and around the donor building is vital for the success of reuse. This applies as much to information creation as the material aspects of the products themselves (location, quality, quantity, etc.). The donor building is the locus in which the work processes, requirements and guidance of various actors is concentrated. The current report only considers the use of reclaimed prefabricated concrete elements, but the questions listed in section 2 could be applied to other materials and products, too.

The work processes checklists are aimed at practical use, which is reflected in its brevity. It is meant to be used by multiple actors in the value chain simultaneously, as they might have responsibilities or interests in various stages of the project. This may structure planning, especially regarding information exchange. For this reason, although the document is nominally linear in shape, actors will notice that work and information in one stage will feed into other stages. Where applicable, it is indicated which stages the work processes are relevant for, in addition to the primary stage. The phases pertaining to business and life cycle assessment (LCA) are not always explicitly singled out in the

checklists, because all issues revolving around reuse are ultimately relevant for business decisions. In the interest of clarity, the most important links to other phases are emphasised. Importantly, with buildings constructed by many different companies and deconstructed by yet other companies, it is often useful to consider other firms not (only) as competitors but also as potential collaborators. In the Dutch language, the neologism 'concullega' is used for this, to indicate that one can be at the same time a competitor and a colleague. This attitude can also point to new forms of collaboration between firms.

ReCreate's deconstruction pilots have been completed and lessons learned have been documented for the various stages (see Vullings et al., 2022; 2024a; 2024b). In terms of information gathered or produced, the deconstruction phase nonetheless morphs into the redesign and reuse phases, as data on materials and products and their characteristics is repurposed by architects and structural engineers in this phase. Data produced and gathered in the deconstruction phase is also needed in the reuse phase in dealings with the authorities (see Halonen et al., 2025). For example, the building permit for the reuse phase will require some extent of data on quality management in order to show the reclaimed elements comply with present building regulations. To a significant degree, work on the quality management takes place before, during and after deconstruction, with the involvement of structural engineers for various tests. Refurbishment, quality control and the requirements of permitting processes 'remake' the reclaimed components into products suitable for reuse, and producing data through testing is an important step in this. Seen from another point of view, architects may have opinions on specific dimensions or other qualities of the reclaimed products, thereby potentially influencing the work of deconstruction. Regarding redesign, structural engineers and/or architects may already single out elements for reuse before deconstruction starts. The forwards and backwards flow of information throughout the value chain about materials and products is a challenging, yet important, aspect of planning a circular project.

The ReCreate project has produced various technical reports on deconstruction (see Vullings et al., 2022; 2024a; 2024b). The work processes checklists given in Section 2 do not go into the detail of specific issues, but rather focuses on general timing, planning and coordination by actors. Deconstruction and reuse need knowledge and people to come together at the right time, at the right place. Planning such projects differs by project because buildings, firms and regulations are different. However, based on the empirical data of the ReCreate project, there are certain issues that emerge in all cases. Co-operation and planning are obviously always part of construction projects, but circular construction requires a much more detailed level of cooperation, as each deconstruction project has its own peculiarities and decision-making moments. Therefore, actors would be wise to reflect on the differences in various stages compared to linear construction, when they plan a circular project.

A work process which is not included here is the tendering of services. Especially if the reuse project is in some way managed or financed by public actors, significant effort must go into proper tendering. In the Finnish case, ReCreate has developed a model for land (plot)

competition that incorporates circular requirements. Other countries may have circularity-promoting tenders. For example, the Dutch donor building 'Prinsenhof', deconstructed by Lagemaat, was a tender of the Dutch province of Gelderland in which an ambitious level of circularity was required. In other cases, tendering may be part of the normal flow of business, but requirements regarding communication and data sharing should be included to smoothen the circular processes.

Section 2 consists of a series of tables for the various stages of circular (de)construction. The simple idea behind this matrix-style table is to assess, by phase, what other phases are involved, and whether the core questions are addressed. The LCA, business and work/policy aspects may be relevant for all work processes, but in specific cases they may be more relevant than in others. Note that (securing) financing of circular projects is not indicated as a separate stage.

The tables will use the following abbreviations: deconstruction company (D), construction company (C), logistics provider (L), refurbishment provider (R), architect (A), structural engineer (SE), material testing consultant (MT, can be semi-public or private), local authorities (LA), LCA consultant (LCA). In the column 'Actor(s)', the order of primary actors is of no importance, as circular construction projects may have many different starting points, as Harala et al. (2023) show. If a table cell is marked with 'x', this means this process has a connection to the phase in that column.

Section 3 provides concluding remarks, and Annex 1 is a printable version of the table used in Section 2, which can be used in planning meetings.

2. Work processes per each reuse process phase

2.1. Pre deconstruction and pre-deconstruction audit

The processes listed here refer to the pre-deconstruction audit and other processes which precede the deconstruction. The work processes listed in Table 1 are generalised from the work processes observed in fieldwork in the ReCreate project. Each project has its own unique aspects and embeddedness in national rules and norms, but these processes should apply to many cases.

The pre-deconstruction audit has its own requirements, which can be found in Vullings et al. (2022). Nevertheless, preparing for a circular construction project starts with selecting the donor building. This implies the necessity of planning logistics, temporary storage and possible refurbishment, too. The time horizon for reuse may be unclear, which is why coordination between actors, including municipalities, is essential. Furthermore, as the economy may change during the planning horizon, it is advisable to draft alternative plans. In some jurisdictions, reclaimed building materials may get a waste status if they are not used within a certain period of time (see Halonen et al., 2025).

2.2. Deconstruction

The analysis of the real-life deconstruction projects of ReCreate can be found in Vullings et al. (2024a; 2024b). More details on the work processes listed in Table 2 can be found in these reports. The deconstruction of the donor building is often a labour-intensive process. In the interest of cost management, it is important that the actors involved in deconstruction, quality control and redesign/reuse plan this phase carefully. Each donor building is different, therefore the need for contingency planning and constant evaluation must be agreed upon between partners. It is advisable to involve local government at an early stage, to pre-empt complicated and time-consuming procedures to some extent. On the business side, it is important to be aware of work safety requirements and the potential need to rent specialised equipment, and select employees or subcontractors with relevant expertise. Currently, there are many ways to label reclaimed materials/products, which also depend on the information systems used by other actors in the value chain.

In this stage, there is a need for very intense planning and deliberation about the deconstruction plan. The deconstruction plan involves many actors, but also depends on the location and this plan already feeds into the need for a logistics and storage plan.

Table 1. **Pre deconstruction** and **pre-deconstruction audit** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
<i>Select suitable donor building (incl. location criteria, site visit)</i>	x	x			x		x		D, C, L, SE, LA	
<i>Apply for deconstruction permit/inform authorities about deconstruction</i>	x	x						x	D, C, SE, LA	
<i>Collect construction drawings & calculations of donor building</i>	x	x	x		x	x			D, SE, A	
<i>Digitise building in BIM model</i>	x	x		(x)	x				D, (R), SE, A, (LA)	
<i>Select materials/ products to be reclaimed</i>	x		x	x	x				D, R, SE, A, MT	
<i>Investigate the presence of hazardous substances</i>			x	x				x	D, (SE), MT	
<i>Perform and report quality tests</i>			x	x	x			x	SE, (R), MT	
<i>Coordinate with other actors for reuse (e.g. input from architects)</i>	x			x	x				D, C, SE, R, A, LA	
<i>Plan efficient deconstruction</i>	x	x					x	x	D, C, SE, L	
<i>Storage planning (incl. permit processes, storage site preparation)</i>	x	x		x	x				D, C, R, L, LA	
<i>Document data needs</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	ALL	

Table 2. **Deconstruction** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	Create structural stability calculations for deconstruction						x		SE, (D)	
x	Create structural deconstruction plan (incl. labelling scheme for tracing)	x	x					x	SE, (D)	
x	Assess need for specialised tools & skills (incl. crane rental & crane work)	x	x				x	x	D	
x	Create work deconstruction plan (and sub-plans, e.g. lifting plan)	x	x				x	x	D, (SE)	
	Assess compliance with construction, environmental and safety regulations							x	D, LA	
	Label materials/products to be reused	x	x	x	x				D, (L)	
	Implement deconstruction (incl. preparatory works, such as stripping and hazardous substances removal)	x	x						D	
	Create contingency plan for unforeseen situations	x	x					x	D, SE, (C)	
	Document data needs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	ALL	

2. 3. Logistics

Table 3 is dominated by transport-related issues. Transport is often a subcontracted part of a (de)construction project. Nevertheless, according to empirical data from ReCreate, transport is a factor that may have significant impact on the viability of circular projects, as it and storage have the potential to inadvertently damage reclaimed materials/products. This should be prevented by careful planning between actors. In addition, temporary storage sites may have their own permitting processes or negotiations attached.

2. 4. Quality management

Table 4 shows in brief the main quality management processes documented in Räsänen et al. (2024a; 2024b). Quality management is an extremely important part of circular projects, because clients and local regulators alike may need reassurance about quality management aspects. The quality of recovered materials and products cannot be simply assumed to be in accordance with standards, like in the case of CE-marking, but often has to be separately established through customised testing and documentation. Mainstreaming of quality management procedures for reclaimed construction products should also enable their viability in business processes, i.e. it could be possible to find a market segment dedicated to these procedures.

It can be argued that after thorough quality management tests, actors know more about the materials/products to be reused than with some virgin materials and structures. Assessing quality is a process that is important for many stages of the reuse project. Not only for 'internal use', i.e. regarding the work of architects and structural engineers, but also as support in dealing with local authorities. Quality management of materials and products helps actors answer questions from authorities and in this way also helps establish trust in reuse. Therefore, quality management procedures could prove a catalyst towards a positive feedback loop in which circular methods become more common.

2. 5. Refurbishment

Table 5 shows refurbishment work processes. For these processes it must be noted that they are highly dependent on which actor does the refurbishment (e.g. the original producer of the products, or another actor) and how the product was installed (i.e. with a structural topping or some other technique). The refurbishment phase is open to many processes, which also carry over to redesign, if e.g. new connections should be installed.

Table 3. **Logistics** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	x	Assess transport costs in relation to donor building, refurbishment and reuse sites (incl. special emissions requirements)		(x)		x	x		D, C, L	
	x	Assess need for specialised transport equipment	x	(x)					D, SE, L	
	x	Label materials for reuse and enter into database(s), material passports	x	x	x	x			D, R, L, SE, MT	
	x	Transport from deconstruction site to temporary storage or refurbishment facility	x	x			x		D, L, R	
		Transport at the refurbishment facility	x	x	x		x		R	
		Transport to reuse site	x	x	x	x	x		L, C	
x	x	Document data needs	x	x	x	x	x	x	ALL	

Table 4. **Quality management** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	x		Review technical drawings	x	x				D, R, SE, MT, C	
			Enlist expertise for material-specific tests (e.g. concrete factory, university, other consultancy)	x	x		x		MT, C	
	x	x	Plan quality control processes with other actors (incl. deconstruction site guidance)	x	x				D, SE, C, MT, R	
	x	x	Plan and implement visual inspection of elements (incl. work site inspection protocol)	x					R, D, C, MT, SE	
x			Select and perform non-destructive tests	x	x		x	x	SE, MT, C	
x			Select and perform (semi-)destructive tests	x	x		x	x	SE, MT, C	
x	x		Document and compare test results with original specifications		x				SE, MT, C	
			Assess structural reusability	x	x				SE, A, C	
x	x	x	Document data needs	x	x	x	x	x	ALL	

Table 5. **Refurbishment** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	x	x	x	Assess general need for refurbishment during/after deconstruction	x				R, SE, D, MT	
	x			Create protocol for work division of refurbishment				x	D, R, SE	
		x	x	Plan internal logistics	x		x		R	
			x	Assign personnel to refurbishment	x			x	R, D	
	x	x	x	Allocate tools and machinery				x	R, D	
			x	Align refurbishment with design needs	x				R, D, SE, A	
		x	x	Implement refurbishment		x			R, MT	

2. 6. Redesign and reuse

Table 6 shows some of the main work processes in redesign, i.e. architects' and structural engineers' work to incorporate reclaimed elements to new building designs, where they are reused. Redesign is dependent on information and materials from the deconstruction and quality management phases and, therefore, work performed in these phases do play a significant role. Of particular interest for this phase is the division of work between architects and structural engineers. It would appear to be sensible to base the redesign on materials/products available rather than try to rigidly fit them into a preconceived (architectural or structural) design. Reuse, then, constitutes of implementing the construction, i.e. the results of the redesign, on a new site. Depending on the redesign solution, it may be more or less similar as building with new components.

2. 7. LCA

Table 7 shows processes that are connected to LCA. Currently, there are many methodologies for performing LCA and the requirements from local authorities in the context of permits may also vary. This list is therefore deliberately general, as depending on the context, LCA data may need to be collected because of regulatory requirements, but the collection can also be motivated from a business perspective (e.g. to acquire green building certification expected by clients). It is however safe to assume that the amount of data required will grow rather than shrink.

2. 8. Business

Table 8 shows some of the work processes that relate to project management. Sairanen (2023) shows much more detail on company roles, potential for scaling up and new value-creation processes. Sairanen (2023) provides business-relevant understanding for companies aspiring to engage in the reuse of precast concrete elements. In particular, Sairanen's report touches upon issues of labour costs and division of work. These two themes run through all work processes in this document. The issue of insurance may not be relevant in all jurisdictions, but from a business perspective it is important to assess the risks involved in a proper manner.

2. 9. Work / employees / policy

Table 9 shows work processes that deal with employees or policy. As documented in Sairanen (2023), much of deconstruction is labour intensive, therefore it is important to train/prepare companies' employees well. To a large extent this is also a form of 'rethinking': given climate change challenges and resource scarcity, it is necessary that policy-makers, businesses and employees all see the value of circular construction.

Table 6. **Redesign and reuse** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	x				<i>Decide the 'idea' of the reuse design/project</i>		x		C, A, SE, D	
			x	x	<i>Compare quality management test results with requirements of reuse project</i>		x		MT, C, SE, R	
	x		x	x	<i>Assess need of refurbishment for reuse project</i>				SE, MT, A, R	
					<i>Contact authorities sufficiently early</i>		x	x	C, SE, A	
x	x				<i>Understand the construction system of donor building regarding dimensions and structural capabilities</i>				C, D, A, SE	
					<i>Understand structural and spatial requirements of reuse project</i>		x		SE, A, C	
	x		x	x	<i>Create BIM model of reuse project</i>	x			A, SE,	
				x	<i>Design connections for reclaimed elements</i>		x		SE, C, A	
				x	<i>Design reuse project with close cooperation between architect and structural engineers (+ other parties, for e.g. installations), including permitting</i>	x	x	x	SE, A, LA, C	
x	x	x	x	x	<i>Document data needs</i>	x	x	x	ALL	

Table 7. **LCA-related** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
				x		Plan data collection and methodology	x	x	C, SE, A, LCA, D, R	
x	x	x		x	x	Collect and send data on energy use, material flows, transport and deconstruction site to e.g. LCA consultants			D, LCA, L, R, C, A, SE	
	x	x	x	x	x	Document (future) data needs for LCA calculations			ALL	

 Table 8. **Business** work processes.

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
	x						Ideation to reduce workload of deconstruction	x	D, SE	
		x	x	x	x		Develop processes to reduce refurbishment needs after deconstruction	x	R	
x	x						Analyse costs of deconstruction		D	
x	x	x	x	x	x		Develop contractual obligations regarding warranties		C, D, R, SE	
		x		x			Assess costs of storage	x	D, L, R,	
				x	x		Assess market value of reuse		C, R	
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Develop contract templates for reuse	x	ALL	
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Document data needs	x	ALL	

Table 9. *Employee- and policy-related work processes.*

Pre deconstruction	Deconstruction	Logistics	Quality	Refurbishment	Redesign & reuse	LCA	Business	Work/policy	Actor(s)	Mark completed
x	x			x	x			Hold workshops and training to prepare for work	D, C, R, A, SE	
	x			x				Provide detailed information on safety procedures	D, L, R, C, SE	
	x	x	x	x	x	x		Provide training for BIM and specialised tools	D, SE, C, A	
	x			x	x		x	Include employees in evaluation and lessons learned	D, SE, L, C, R, A	
	x						x	Guide employees' mindset towards reclamation	D	
x	x							Collaboration between deconstruction firm and structural engineers in work instructions	D, SE	
x	x	x	x	x	x	x		Raise awareness of relevant policy norms	D, L, R, SE, A, LA, LCA	
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Document data needs	ALL	

3. Conclusion

In circular construction projects, there are many ways to organise work. Given a near endless diversity in buildings, materials and reuse needs, it is nearly impossible to provide an exhaustive list of work processes. This document itself is an amalgamation of work process found in the Finnish, Swedish, Dutch and German clusters of the ReCreate project. Therefore, some processes may be more relevant to some countries than to others. For example, the processes around insurance have emerged nearly exclusively from the German cluster.

Additionally, firms are also different in their interests and competences. The ReCreate project is very much an example of 'learning by doing' – if one solution does not work, another will be tried. This involves the knowledge and skills of multiple actors, and since the ReCreate project deals with 'old' buildings, it is very valuable to have project employees with experience going back to the 1970s or even earlier.

The work processes in this document are not neatly compartmentalised processes, but rather they are part of iterative processes of learning and information exchange between project actors. In this sense, circular construction projects seem to be an example of 'the whole is more than its parts'.

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